

PECULIARITIES OF THE FORMATION OF A KNOWLEDGE-BASED ECONOMY IN GEORGIA**Giguashvili Giuli,***PhD in Economics, Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Makasarashvili Tamar,***PhD in Economics, Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Khorguashvili Tea,***PhD in Economics, Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Bebnadze Khatuna***PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Abstract**

In globalization, the primary way to increase the country's competitiveness in the world market is to improve education and increase human capital. The transition to the knowledge economy is a long-term process and requires fundamental changes in the education system. The traditional mission of the education system - informational education - has become a thing of the past. Today, the main priority is developing a quality education system and supporting science, technology, and innovation.

The development of a knowledge-based, innovative economy is a necessary condition for increasing Georgia's competitiveness. Several reforms were implemented to improve the education system, ensure macroeconomic stability, attract foreign investments, develop foreign trade, and economically integrate Georgia with the European Union. However, social policy and human capital development remain challenges for our country.

Numerous scientific studies have been devoted to determining the connection between the level of knowledge and economic growth. New strategies and policy documents are being created, the analysis of which and the development of recommendations for monetary policy improvement are the main goals of the paper.

The article presents the main challenges of the Georgian education system and evaluates the role of human capital and innovation in the development of the economy.

Keywords: Knowledge Economy, Human Capital, Economic Policy.

Introduction. Knowledge is a form of storing and systematizing the results of human cognitive activity, which helps us rationally organize our activities and solve the encountered problems. A knowledge-based economy, which involves using knowledge technologies to obtain economic benefits, maximize profits, and create jobs, is referred to in the monetary literature as the knowledge economy. The knowledge economy mainly focuses on the acquisition and management of knowledge.

Innovations in the field of education are the basis of economic growth. For the education system of Georgia to be competitive, it is necessary to modernize it, raise the quality of financing and autonomy of educational institutions, harmonize the education system with international Western standards, etc.

Research reason. The paper aims to analyze the achievements and challenges of the Georgian education system and determine the role of human capital and innovation in the knowledge economy.

Methodology. The research is based on analytical, quantitative, and statistical methods.

Literature review. Human capital is the primary resource of the economic and innovative development of the country. According to the World Bank, 64% of the world's wealth is in human capital, a large part of which is the workers' knowledge and intellectual abilities. In the book, "The Dynamic Forces of Capitalist Development," Arthur Madison argues that a 1% increase in investment in education leads to a 0.35% increase in gross domestic product. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, based on the analysis of the facts

collected by it, concludes that an increase in the average statistical duration of education by one year leads to - an increase in the GDP of the respective country by 3-6%. [1]

Today, human capital is considered a complex, intensive factor in the development of the economy and society, and its quality is directly proportional to the growth and competitiveness of the country's economy. The main directions of their implementation are directly related to increasing the competitiveness of human capital, which is one of the leading resources of the country's economic and innovative development. [2]

The founders of the concept of human capital are Alfred Marshall, John Bates Clark, Irving Fisher, and others. In the second half of the 20th century, G. Becker, M. Blaug, S. Bowles, F. Makhlup, J. Mintzer, O. Nordhaug, M. Fisher, T. Schultz, and others developed the Theory of Human Capital. In their works, Georgian researchers - M. Julakidze, N. Basaria, M. Toria, A. Abralava, E. Baratashvili, and others discussed modern views on various aspects of the Theory of Human Capital. [2]

The main factor of the transition to the knowledge economy in the conditions of globalization is the raising of the level of knowledge and the formation of those professionals who can invent, implement, and generate innovations of new innovative products, technologies, and services. Studies confirm that the higher the share of educated people in the country's total population, the higher the economic level in these countries is. Thus, an effective education system is a necessity for knowledge economy formation. The main

priority of the education system is the formation of creative and critical thinking and the development of independent information search, processing, in-depth analysis, and application skills.

Discussion/Results. Countries that recognize the transformative power of education in shaping individuals, promoting economic growth and social development; that have well-funded education systems, world-class universities, and an emphasis on research and critical thinking; Those who have developed a highly educated population, who make a significant contribution to the growth of their economy, are leaders in global education rankings.

According to Wisevoter (<https://wisevoter.com/>), the ten most educated countries in the world, according to their higher education scores and rankings, are South Korea (69.29%), Canada (66.36%), Japan (64.81%), Luxembourg (63.12%), Ireland (62.88%), Russia (62.09%), Lithuania (57.48%), Great Britain (57.47%), the Netherlands (55, 60%) and Norway (55.03%). As for Georgia, our country ranks 43rd in the world ranking of educated countries, with 28.4%. [3]

By prioritizing education, a highly skilled workforce is formed, and innovation is stimulated, which leads to economic growth. Economist Anthony Bernard-Sasges believes that "Human capital underpins the economic potential of every city. Human capital encompasses the collective knowledge and skills of a city population. It reflects the dynamics between educational attainment, innovation, and demographics across metropolitan areas. Cities with diverse, highly skilled workforces and innovative businesses are better positioned to adapt to technological change and

✚ Georgia		Ranked in the World	Global Average
Average IQ	84.5	#84	82
School Achievement	9.16%	#55	15.1%
Intelligence Capital Index	31.5	#58	34
Literacy Rate	99.76%	#17	86.5%

Source: <https://wisevoter.com/>

Statistical data proves that Georgia's world ranking in education indicators is relatively low. What kind of economy we will have in the future will be determined by the efficiency of our education system and the state choice of Georgia. It is the prerogative of the state policy to determine how the resources in the country will be distributed in different areas and how much it will be possible to use the accumulated knowledge as efficiently as possible. The main goal of the education system is to provide high quality, which will empower individuals to make the best choices for developing their competencies and abilities. It will contribute to a sustainable, knowledge-based, and assertive civil society formation. Currently, the career system, remuneration, pension policy, and educational programs operating in Georgia do not sufficiently contribute to highly qualified and effective personnel development and maintenance in higher education and research fields, and applied research projects are rarely implemented. Specific governance, funding, and accountability challenges remain in the higher education and research sectors.

compete globally in today's knowledge-based economy." [4]

Cities that lead in the human capital category are centers of higher education and business innovation. London leads the ranking. It has top-ranked universities in many cities around the world. Tokyo ranks second in the human capital category and remains a global center for innovation. Riyadh - The Saudi capital is in third place. Abu Dhabi (#8), like Riyadh, has a young population and high funding for education. New York, Seoul, Paris, and Sydney all topped the rankings. All four are known for both educational institutions and business development. Residents of Washington (#7) and Boston (#10) are distinguished by a high level of education. [4]

IQ was created to measure human intelligence. It usually ranges from 0 to 200. The higher the IQ of an individual, the more intelligent he ought to be. A nation's average IQ gives a general idea of both education and where social and economic wealth lies. Measuring a country's intelligence is a difficult task. The Intelligence Capital Index (ICI), which considers education and innovation, research and development, and social and economic factors, was created For a complete assessment.

Japan (106.48) is the most intelligent country in the world, Taiwan (106.47) the second smartest, Singapore (105.89) the third, Hong Kong (105.37) ranked fourth, and China (104.1) the fifth. These countries invest heavily in education. Therefore, they have strong market economies. Georgia ranks 84th among 193 countries in the Smartest Countries ranking. [5]

Investment bank Galt & Taggart conducted an interesting study on the current trends in the education sector of Georgia. According to research:

Georgia's education sector revenues grew at an 18.7% CAGR over 2021-23, a significant acceleration from the 10.7% CAGR over 2013-21. Increased government spending, the influx of international students, costlier tuition fees, and growing enrollments in private schools supported this growth. While the government remains the primary source of revenue for the sector, the private sector is rapidly gaining traction. In 2023, private sector revenue increased by 25.5% y/y, reaching GEL 958.2 mln.

General education sector revenue was up 15.5% y/y to GEL 1.5 bn in 2023, primarily driven by increased government spending, while private sector revenue also posted growth. Higher enrolments and increased tuition fees fueled growth in private sector revenue. Enrollment in private schools is expected to rise more, reaching 73.1k pupils by the 2028/29 academic year, up from the current 66.5k.

Higher education sector revenue was up 19.6% y/y to GEL 1.1bn in 2023. Revenue growth stemmed from

the increased tuition fees, rising intake of the old age groups, and an increasing number of international students, particularly from India. Georgia's attractiveness to international students is bolstered by affordable tuition, living expenses, and improved direct air links with India and the Middle East. Looking forward, Georgia is poised to sustain growth in foreign student enrollment, potentially hosting 48,000 international students in 2028, contributing an estimated US\$ 500 mln to the economy. [6]

In 2022, with the support of the World Bank and the French Development Agency, a human capital program was launched to establish a knowledge economy and develop human capital in Georgia. The program aims to increase the country's economic growth potential by investing in health care, education, and social protection. To support the human capital program, the World Bank allocated an investment worth 455 million US dollars, and the French Development Agency (AFD) provided co-financing of 100 million euros. [7]

Allocation of Funds by Sectors

Source: <https://projects.worldbank.org/en/projects-operations/project-detail/P175455>

The human capital program envisages the transformation of Georgia's education system in early education, general and university education, and subsequent stages. According to the Georgia Human Capital Review prepared by the World Bank, developing human capital to respond to the challenges of productivity, aging, and inclusion is critical for Georgia to ensure sustainable and inclusive growth of the country.

The government document, the development strategy of Georgia - "Vision 2030" fully presents the state policy and strategy in the education and science system [8]. According to it, By 2030, the development and implementation of evidence-based policies and programs that are the basis for the development of individuals and institutions will be achieved. The education system will be based on universally recognized, modern standards; the education system's effective management mechanisms will be made; Science will become the basis of the knowledge-based economy; human capital, academic staff, researchers, and individuals generally employed in education and training as well as research and innovation systems will be invested.

The government's goal is to promote result-oriented science, which, in turn, means defining research topics focused on the UN Sustainable Development Goals and supporting research focused on global and national needs. The government policy aim is to promote a sustainable and inclusive entrepreneurial innovation ecosystem and create more innovation opportunities. Promote academic entrepreneurship collaboration with industry, public sector, and civil society. Flexible and effective management mechanisms will be launched to strengthen scientific research, innovation, and entrepreneurship. A new model of cooperation between science and business will be created to heighten the commercialization of science.

The activities carried out by the Innovation and Technology Agency for an innovative ecosystem

formation in Georgia are significant. Within ten years of its establishment, more than 200 innovative startups were financed - with approximately 38 million GEL within the grant programs. As a result, the beneficiaries generated half a billion GEL of private financial benefits and created 3 thousand new jobs. With the agency's support, the top 3 accelerator "500" entered Georgia. Along with Georgian, international startups also participate in the international-level acceleration program. This fact emphasizes the role of Georgia as a regional innovation hub. As a result of the acceleration program, the first private venture fund with a capital of 20 million dollars was created in 2022 in Georgia. Nine technoparks have been made throughout Georgia, which assist citizens with innovative ideas in implementing various projects on the one window principle.

Georgia offers international companies operating in specific industries a favorable business environment in opening R&D offices in the country, which will contribute to competitive competencies development on the ground and create tens of thousands of highly paid jobs in the future. The state is actively involved in making an appropriate environment for local investment potential promotion in training sessions, events, and various meetings of the private sector and their representatives, which will help raise the awareness of the business sector in the direction of the innovation ecosystem.

Conclusion. Thus, it is indisputable that high human capital is a prerequisite for maximizing overall social benefits. A necessary condition for the sustainable development of Georgia's economy is the improvement of human capital and the increase in the efficiency of the education system, in which a significant role, together with the private sector, belongs to the state. It is necessary to develop practice-based programs in educational institutions that will consider the needs of the labor market and innovative approaches in the teaching and learning field to make the human capital supply system in Georgia more

effective and inclusive. It is necessary to bring the quality assurance standards of higher education closer to European standards.

We hope that realizing tasks envisaged by the development strategy of Georgia's "Vision 2030" will yield beneficial results and a knowledge-based market economy will finally be established in our country.

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